

Potato cultivation in agrivoltaic systems in Northern Italy: a four-year case study on array setup, shading patterns, and yield response

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ABSTRACT

Agrivoltaic (APV) systems offer a promising approach to co-locating food and energy production; however, their effects on crop performance remain insufficiently quantified, particularly for shade-sensitive crops such as potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.).

This study reports a four-year field experiment (2021–2024) conducted in Northern Italy under a REM Tec Agrovoltaico® dual-axis sun-tracking APV system. The objective was to quantify potato yield response and tuber characteristics under contrasting array setups and associated shading patterns, including the adoption of an anti-tracking (AT) management strategy during critical growth stages.

Experimental treatments included a full-light control (FL), standard sun-tracking (ST1), intensified shading (ST2), and a dynamic anti-tracking strategy applied during the tuber initiation phase in 2024 in combination with ST1 (ST1+AT).

Yield response was strongly dependent on both shading intensity and timing. The standard sun-tracking configuration (ST1), characterized by a low mean seasonal shade depth (~13 %), resulted in limited yield penalties (–12 % on average), whereas the higher-shade configuration (ST2) caused yield reductions exceeding 30 %.

The AT management during early tuber development partially mitigated yield losses, indicating that dynamic light management can represent an effective strategy to balance agricultural productivity and energy generation in APV systems. Weibull-based modelling of tuber size distribution (TSD) revealed a consistent shift toward smaller tubers under increasing shade, while tuber dry matter content (DMC) remained relatively stable.

1. Introduction

Agrivoltaic (APV) systems — the simultaneous use of land for agricultural production and photovoltaic electricity generation — are receiving increasing attention as a promising solution for sustainable land use in regions under pressure from climate change and energy transition goals [1,2]. However, the integration of crops under photovoltaic (PV) panels presents complex trade-offs between light availability, crop physiology, and yield performance, particularly in sun-loving crops such as potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.).

In southern and Mediterranean climates, where solar irradiance is typically high, moderate shading from PV structures may offer potential agronomic benefits by mitigating heat and water stress [3,4]. Yet, this

benefit is highly context-dependent and varies with crop type, shading intensity, microclimatic conditions, and management practices. The potato crop, despite its widespread global cultivation and importance, has been relatively underrepresented in APV research, with only a limited number of studies available [5–10]. These studies often report yield penalties under APV systems, but outcomes differ according to the degree of shading and seasonal conditions. Recent findings from a temperate-climate study on rice cultivation under APV conditions [11] corroborate these trade-offs. The authors observed a 15–23 % yield reduction under APV, varying with seasonal conditions, but also reported microclimatic benefits such as lower canopy temperatures and reduced physiological stress. These results reinforce the idea that APV performance is both crop-specific and climate-sensitive, further

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supporting the need for context-based system design and systematic field validation.

While the traditional “food versus energy” framing of APVs is evolving, informed crop selection and system design remain essential to avoid productivity trade-offs [12,13]. Notably, shading under APV is dynamic and differs sharply from the uniform light reduction under shade nets, often leading to rapid sunshade transitions that affect stomatal behaviour and crop physiology [14]. In such systems, maintaining crop productivity close to 100 % of FL conditions is possible, but only if crop selection and system operation are carefully optimized [2,4,15]. In this context, sun-tracking PV systems offer both opportunities and risks: they may intensify shading compared to fixed structures [4], but also enable adaptive control through anti-tracking (AT) strategies, whereby shading is reduced during critical phenological windows [16].

Crop simulation models are increasingly important tools for designing and managing APV systems [17,18]. However, their use in simulating crop responses under the heterogeneous and dynamic shading conditions of APV systems remains limited, and current models may need further refinement to account for light acclimation and spatial variability. Addressing these modelling challenges through refined calibration strategies is essential for developing reliable predictive tools for APV systems. A promising conceptual framework for improving model parameterization under such heterogeneous conditions was recently outlined [19,20] emphasizing the need for dynamic adjustments in photosynthetic parameters in response to light variability, a perspective particularly relevant for crops grown under APV-induced shade fluctuations. This is particularly true for shade-sensitive crops like potato, where default model parameters may underestimate the impact of reduced and fluctuating photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) on photosynthesis and assimilate partitioning. Addressing these modelling challenges through refined calibration strategies is essential for developing reliable predictive tools for APV systems.

Rather than positioning the modelling component as a full calibration effort, the objective is to explore its interpretive value in explaining year-to-year variability and physiological mechanisms affected by shade. The data assembled over four years represent a unique resource to test hypotheses on shading thresholds, tuber initiation sensitivity, and canopy acclimation in Mediterranean organic production systems.

Rather than pursuing a full model calibration, our modelling effort serves as a conceptual bridge, linking measured yield responses to known physiological mechanisms, and lays the groundwork for future extensions toward dynamic APV-crop simulations.

The main objective of this study was to assess the agronomic feasibility of potato cultivation under contrasting agrivoltaic shading configurations in a Mediterranean organic farming context, with particular emphasis on yield formation and tuber size distribution. Specifically, we aimed to

- (i) quantify yield and quality responses under different shading intensities and timing relative to key phenological stages, and
- (ii) explore the interpretive value of a process-based crop model in linking observed yield patterns to known physiological responses to shading.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Experimental site and agrivoltaic setups

The study was conducted at a large commercial APV installation (REM Tec, Agrovoltaico® ver. 1.1) located in Borgo Virgilio, Italy (Mantova; 45°07' N, 10°47' E). The experimental site at Virgilio (Po Valley, northern Italy) is characterized by a deep alluvial soil with loam to sandy-loam texture. The soil profile is homogeneous along the rooting zone, with no restrictive layers within the upper 1.5 m. Main physical properties of the soil profile are reported in Table 1.

The system's structural specifications, including main axis height

Table 1

Physical properties of the soil profile at the Virgilio site (Po Valley, Italy).

Property	Horizons	
	Ap (0–50 cm)	C (50–150 cm)
Clay (%)	22.9	20
Silt (%)	37.7	35
Sand (%)	39.4	45
Organic matter (%)	1.1	0.5
Bulk density (g cm ⁻³)	1.35	1.4
θ _{sat} (cm ³ cm ⁻³)	0.43	0.41
θ _{res} (cm ³ cm ⁻³)	0.08	0.03
α (cm ⁻¹)	0.04	0.02
n (-)	1.56	1.15
K _{sat} (cm h ⁻¹)	2.9	0.95

and spacing, match those described in Agostini et al. [21] and Potenza et al. [22]. The Agrovoltaico® system (Fig. 1) is an elevated, dual-axis solar tracking structure. Horizontal main axes are mounted on stilts, while secondary axes, hinged perpendicularly to the main axes, support the solar panels arranged in a 2-portrait (2P) configuration. Panel orientation is controlled by electric motors with wireless communication, allowing rotation along two orthogonal axes. Vertical supports along the main rotation axis are spaced at a pitch of 12 m. The main characteristics of the photovoltaic modules are reported in Table 2, while system-level layout and operational features are summarized in the same table. Detailed electrical specifications of the modules are provided in Agostini et al. [21] and related studies. Additionally, to provide context for the agrivoltaic trade-off, electricity production was estimated for the standard sun-tracking configuration (ST1) and for the temporary anti-tracking strategy (ST1+AT) using a simulation framework developed at UCSC (Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore). The platform is implemented in Python and relies on the PVLIB library to simulate solar energy conversion (Table 2). The anti-tracking strategy was applied only once during the growing season, during the tuber initiation phase (approximately May). Consequently, the reduction in electricity generation was limited to this period, while energy production during the remaining months followed the standard sun-tracking configuration.

2.1.1. Agrivoltaic setups (Shading scenarios)

Four independent field experiments were conducted between 2021 and 2024 within the Borgo Virgilio APV system. While each experiment shared a common structure, the specific shading treatments varied slightly across years, due to deliberate design evolution. All shading scenarios are summarized in Table 3.

2.1.1.1. Agrovoltaico® (Scenario ST1). Tested each year, this scenario corresponds to the unmodified Agrovoltaico® system with a ground cover ratio (GCR) < 0.14, resulting in moderate shading (mean shade depth ~ 21 %). Shade depth s_d represents the relative seasonal reduction in intercepted radiation compared to the FL condition. It was computed as:

$$s_d = 100 \cdot \frac{(I_{FL} - I_{sa})}{I_{FL}} \quad (1)$$

where I_{FL} is the seasonal total intercepted radiation (photosynthetically active radiation, PAR) in the (FL) control and I_{sa} is the corresponding value in a given shaded area. The resulting percentage quantifies the extent of shading as experienced by the crop. The abbreviation “ST” refers to sun-tracking mode.

2.1.1.2. Shading net (Scenario ST2 – 2021 only). In 2021, a high-density shading net of size 5 m x 12 m was horizontally installed beneath the PV panels to enhance shading. In this treatment, the concept of (CGR) was adapted to reflect the effective projected shade of the net over the test

Fig. 1. 3D rendering of the agro-photovoltaic structures adopted in the experiments.

Table 2

Main characteristics of the photovoltaic modules used in the agrivoltaic system.

Parameter	Value
PV module manufacturer	Yingli Green Energy
Module series	YLM 72 Cell – 40 mm
Cell technology	Monocrystalline silicon
Nominal power (STC)	325 Wp
Module efficiency	17 %
Module dimensions	1960 × 990 × 40 mm
Module weight	25.5 kg
Tracking configuration	Biaxial sun-tracking
Installed PV capacity	2.147 MWp
Electricity production (ST1)	1445.174 MWh during potato growing season (April–July)
Electricity production (ST1+AT)	1244.7 MWh during potato growing season (April–July)
Anti-tracking application	During tuber initiation (~ May)

area. The net covered 60 m² and was deployed above a 12 × 12 m reference plot (144 m²). Considering an estimated shading rate of 90 %, the effective shaded area was approximately 54 m², resulting in CGR ~ 0.375. Although the shading arrangements differed between 2021 (net) and 2022 (larger PV panels, CGR = 0.41), both configurations were classified as “ST2”, due to their comparable shading intensity.

2.1.1.3. *Enlarged PV panels (Scenario ST2 – 2022–2023)*. To increase shading, a wooden frame (3 m × 4 m) covered with a black polyethylene film was mounted over the original panels (0.998 m × 2.065 m), Fig. 2. Panel movement followed the standard sun-tracking algorithm.

2.1.1.4. *Anti-tracking management (Scenario ST1+AT – 2024)*. This scenario tested the effect of shade reduction during the critical phenological phase by rotating the secondary axis 90° counter to the sun, minimizing both PV exposure and cast shadow. The AT strategy was

Table 3

Tested shading scenarios in the four experimentation years.

Year	Scenarios (main plots)	AV system	sun-track	Height of main rotation axis (m)	Mean shade – depth (%)	GCR	Potato cultivar	Test areas established (main plots) (N)	Number of shading areas (sub-plots) (N)
2021	FL	-	-	-	0	-	Kuroda	1	4
	ST1	REM-Tec 3D 1.1	yes	5	20 %	0.135	Kuroda	1	
2022	ST2	Shading net 90 %	no	5	37.5 %	0.375	Kuroda	1	4
	FL	-	-	-	0	-	Alouette	2	
	ST1	REM-Tec 3D 1.1	yes	5	21 %	0.135	Alouette	2	
	ST2	REM-Tec 3D 1.1 + added black screen	yes	5	42.3 %	0.41	Alouette	2	
2023	FL	-	-	-	0	-	Alouette	2	4
	ST2	REM-Tec 3D 1.1 + added black screen	yes	5	42.3 %	0.41	Alouette	1	
2024	FL	-	-	-	0	-	Alouette	2	5
	ST1	REM-Tec 3D 1.1	yes	5	20.4 %	0.135	Alouette	2	
	ST1+AT	REM-Tec 3D 1.1	yes	5	17 %	0.135	Alouette	2	

AV: agrivoltaic system; GCR: ground cover ratio. Test areas correspond to main plots, while shading areas correspond to sub-plots.

intentionally restricted to the tuber initiation phase, which represents a critical and largely irreversible stage in potato development. Shading during this period primarily affects tuber set and sink establishment, whereas later growth stages show a greater capacity for compensation. Limiting AT to this phenological window therefore allowed us to target the most sensitive phase while minimizing the duration of altered system operation.

2.1.1.5. *Full light (Scenario FL)*. This reference scenario was tested in all years and represents standard potato cultivation without shading. It was set up adjacent to the APV installation over a 144 m² area.

2.1.2. *Agricultural practices, data collection, and analysis*

2.1.2.1. *Crop management*. Potato was planted each year, in a different portion of the experimental field to prevent phytopathological issues linked to continuous monoculture. All trials were conducted according to EU organic farming regulations, with certified practices for weed and pest control. Standard tillage operations for potato were applied. The cultivars used were ‘Kuroda’ (2021) and ‘Alouette’ (2022–2024), both suited for organic production. Irrigation was managed based on seasonal evapotranspiration (ETc) and rainfall and applied via low-pressure drip systems with volume control. Although the exact amount and timing of irrigation were not recorded in detail, soil moisture was monitored to avoid crop water stress during each growth cycle. Crop management information is summarized in Table 4.

2.1.2.2. *Weather data*. Hourly temperature, precipitation, shortwave radiation, relative humidity, and wind speed were recorded by a Delta-T Devices automatic weather station located approximately 50 m from the APV system, in full sun conditions.

Fig. 2. View of the ST2 APV system obtained by modifying the original REM Tec, Agrovoltaico® 3D 1.1, using enlarged PV panels.

Table 4
Potato crop management in the four years.

Year	Potato cultivar	Planting density (plant m ⁻²)	Planting date dd/mm/yyyy	Harvest date dd/mm/yyyy	Total supplied N* (kg ha ⁻¹)	Irrigation (mm)
2021	Kuroda	5.33	29/03/2021	29/07/2021	60	280
2022	Alouette	4.8	18/03/2022	26/07/2022	60	250
2023	Alouette	4.16	31/03/2023	21/07/2023	50	240
2024	Alouette	4.16	10/04/2024	25/07/2024	50	rained

* Pelleted manure, N ~ 3 %.

2.1.3. Radiation mapping and intra-plot subdivision

In each experimental year, ground-level radiation was mapped for all scenarios using the AGV-UCSC platform [4,17,22], with a spatial resolution of 0.12 m² and a temporal resolution of 15 min. The resulting high-resolution maps allowed us to sample a representative gradient of light conditions within each treatment, enabling a more accurate analysis of intra-plot variability across shading scenarios.

Based on these maps, each main plot (144 m²) was subdivided into 4 or 5 shading areas (subplots), each characterized by a distinct seasonal mean shade depth. The exact number of zones varied slightly across years due to improvements in resolution and data processing, while four zones were typically used, a fifth was added in 2024 to better capture subtle differences in radiation exposure (see Fig. 3A and B). Although the agrivoltaic field layout generated spatial heterogeneity in shading at the plot scale, all measurements and data analyses were conducted at the level of shading zones (subplots), which represent the actual experimental units. Main plots were used exclusively to replicate the spatial radiation patterns, not as sampling units.

All key details of treatments, such as system type, tracking mode, GCR, shading level, and number of shading areas, are summarized in Table 3. This design allowed for a comprehensive comparison of potato response to different APV configurations under real operational conditions.

2.1.3.1. Morphological measurements. In 2021 and 2022, detailed morphological traits of potato—plant height, leaf area index (LAI), and specific leaf area (SLA)—were measured on site in Borgo Virgilio (MN, Italy) under the full-light control (FL), the standard sun-tracking

Fig. 3a. Spatial distribution of shade depth within a representative test area. Shade depth is reported as a fraction (0–1) in the scale bar. The diagram illustrates the subdivision of the test area into shading areas (sub-plots; areas 1 to 5) based on shade depth gradients generated by panel positioning and sun movement within the Agrovoltaico® system. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

agrivoltaic configuration (ST1), and the high-shade configuration (ST2), each applied to three replicate plots. The same methodology was followed in 2023 and 2024; however, only two sampling dates per year were conducted, which were considered insufficient for the objectives of the present work. Therefore, only data from 2021 to 2022 are reported here.

Plant height was recorded at multiple growth stages by measuring the distance from ground level to the tip of the main shoot using a measuring tape. Three representative plants per subplot were measured, with four subplots per treatment, resulting in a total of 12 measurements per treatment and sampling date. Mean plant height and standard deviation were used for subsequent analyses. Inclined plants were measured along their natural inclination.

LAI was determined in situ using a SunScan canopy analysis system (SunScan ceptometer, Delta-T Devices, Cambridge, UK). On each date, three below-canopy PAR readings were taken per plot using the probe positioned within the potato canopy, along with simultaneous above-canopy PAR measurements via the external sensor. To avoid interference from artificial shading caused by PV panels, all measurements were performed during time windows when panel shading was minimal or absent (typically around solar noon). This ensured that the resulting LAI values reflected only the canopy’s radiation interception and not the structural shading imposed by the system. One LAI value was computed per plot per date. SLA was measured on four to six sampling dates during the growing season. For each plot, nine fully expanded and healthy leaves from the upper canopy were excised. Immediately after excision, leaves were placed in refrigerated containers and transported to the

Fig. 3b. Schematic representation of the experimental layout within a representative portion of the agrivoltaic system (2022). The diagram indicates the different agrivoltaic scenarios (ST1 and ST2), each corresponding to a main plot. Dashed internal divisions represent shading areas (sub-plots) characterized by different shade depth. Full-light (FL) control plots were located outside the agrivoltaic structure on adjacent areas. The distance between main plots along the system axis was 12 m. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

laboratory, where they were stored at 4 °C and processed within 24 h. Leaf area was determined on fresh material by scanning one-sided leaf area using a leaf area scanner. Subsequently, samples were oven-dried at 65 °C in a ventilated oven until constant weight (approximately 48 h) and weighed to determine dry mass. SLA was calculated as the ratio between one-sided leaf area and leaf dry mass and expressed in $\text{cm}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$.

Morphological traits (plant height, LAI, SLA) measured in 2021 and 2022 were reported as mean \pm standard deviation for each treatment and sampling date. Given the exploratory scope of these measurements and their variable temporal frequency, no inferential analysis (e.g., ANOVA) was conducted. This approach aimed to highlight shading effects on crop morphology without overinterpreting short-term variability.

2.1.3.2. Potato harvest, tuber classes, and DMC. Harvesting was facilitated with a potato digger followed by manual collection. For tuber size distribution analyses, data were pooled within shading zones, as the objective was to characterize distributional responses along the shade depth gradient rather than to compare individual plots. Fresh weight and count per size class (<25, 25–35, 35–45, 45–55, 55–65, 65–75, 75–85 mm) were recorded. For each replicate, ~ 800 g of tubers (>35 mm) were sampled, sliced, oven-dried at 105 °C until constant weight. Dry matter content (DMC) was expressed as a fraction (g g^{-1} fresh weight).

2.1.3.3. Tuber size distribution (TSD). TSD was modelled using the Weibull distribution, known for flexibility with right-skewed data [23,

24], in contrast with Gaussian fits used in earlier works [25,26].

The Weibull distribution for TSD can be defined by the function:

$$f(d) = \left(\frac{k}{\lambda}\right) \left(\frac{d}{\lambda}\right)^{k-1} \exp\left(-\left(\frac{d}{\lambda}\right)^k\right) \quad (2)$$

where:

λ : scale parameter (mm), representing characteristic tuber diameter; k : shape parameter, with $3 < k < 6$, indicating uniformity (larger k means more uniform size).

Parameters λ and k were estimated by least-squares optimization using the datafit function in Scilab (2025).

Known probability densities for the tuber classes d_1, \dots, d_{nc} were estimated with:

$$\hat{y}_j = \frac{n_j}{\sum_{j=1}^{nc} n_j} \frac{1}{d_j - d_{j-1}} \quad (3)$$

where n_j is the number of tubers in class j , and $nc = 6$ with constant bin width (10 mm).

The distribution mean μ was calculated as:

$$\mu = \lambda \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{k}\right) \quad (4)$$

where Γ is the gamma function. The Weibull distribution is therefore presented as a descriptive and comparative tool used to support the agronomic interpretation of tuber size responses to heterogeneous shading, not as an objective of the study.

2.1.3.4. Statistical analysis of tuber yield. A mixed-model ANOVA was used to analyze tuber yield, tuber number, and dry matter content (DMC). Scenario was treated as a fixed factor, while sub-plots nested within main plots were included as random effects. Each year was analyzed independently due to differences in experimental configurations. In the experimental design, each test area corresponded to a main plot (scenario), and the internal shading areas were considered sub-plots characterized by different shade depth. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$, and post-hoc comparisons were performed using Tukey's HSD test.

2.1.3.5. Shade-tuber yield relationship. To quantify the intensity of shading experienced by each experimental area, a variable named shade depth (s_d) was defined. It was used in previous APV studies (e.g. [22,27]) to compute shading levels and their correlation with crop morphological traits.

To examine the *shade – tuber yield relation* each shading area was characterized by a seasonal value of and the marketable yield normalized by the FL value (namely relative yield, y_r) of each individual plot replicate was paired to the corresponding shade depth value. The pairing was carried out for all data collected over the four years of the study. A broken line model was used for the relationship between shade and tuber yield. Segmented or broken line models are regression models in which the relationships between the response and one or more explanatory variables are piecewise linear, i.e. represented by two or more straight lines connected at unknown values. These values are usually referred as breakpoints, or cut-off points. The potato tolerance to shading in a given environment requires a breakpoint $\text{for } s_d = s_{dc}$ and zero slope for increasing values of s_d in the range $0 \dots s_{dc}$. Assuming a constant decrease of y_r for $s_d > s_{dc}$ the model can be described with:

$$y_r = \begin{cases} 1 - b(s_d - s_{dc}) & \text{if } s_d > s_{dc} \\ 1 & \text{if } s_d \leq s_{dc} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The unknowns of the model are the slope b and the breakpoint s_{dc} . The alternative model “absence of shade tolerance” was tested assuming $s_{dc} = 0$. The two unknown parameters were estimated with the least-

squares optimization procedure (*datafit* function, Scilab, [28]). The fitting results and performances of the two models were evaluated with the procedure described by Yang et al. [29].

2.2. Simulations with daisy crop model

The Daisy model was employed to simulate tuber yield responses to spatially variable shading conditions. Daisy is a process-based model capable of simulating key soil–plant–atmosphere interactions, including:

- Soil water movement (Richards' equation)
- Solute transport (convection–dispersion)
- Soil organic matter dynamics (multi-pool decomposition)
- Crop phenology driven by radiation and temperature

Canopy gross photosynthesis is calculated using a non-rectangular hyperbola light response function [30], where light absorption follows Beer's Law as a function of absorbed PAR, LAI, and a light extinction coefficient. The model computes photosynthesis for each canopy layer as:

$$P_i = x \cdot \Delta LAI_i \cdot F_m \cdot \left(1 - \exp\left(\frac{-\varepsilon S_{a,i}}{F_m LAI_i}\right) \right) \quad (6)$$

where:

- P_i = gross photosynthesis per layer [$\text{g CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$]
- x = crop fraction of LAI;
- $S_{a,i}$ = absorbed PAR in layer i [W m^{-2}];
- ε = light use efficiency at low PAR [$(\text{g CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1})/(\text{W m}^{-2})$];
- F_m = photosynthetic capacity at saturated PAR [$\text{g CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$].

To account for shading variability under APV systems, Daisy was coupled to the AGV-UCSC platform. High-resolution maps of shortwave radiation (0.5 m spatial resolution, 15-min timestep) were generated using the APV shading model. For each experimental plot, a radiation file was created—i.e., a time series of radiation values (global and diffuse) specific to that spatial location. Each plot was assigned the nearest file based on geometric centroid. The two soil horizons reported in Table 1 were used to construct the soil input file for Daisy, providing the physical and hydraulic properties required for the simulations.

The default parameterization for potato ('Agria') in Daisy did not reproduce yield patterns under shading. Literature shows that potato physiology (including photosynthetic capacity and phenological timing) is highly responsive to shade (e.g., [31,32]). Since Daisy does not allow dynamic acclimation of photosynthetic parameters during the simulation, a static parameter set is inadequate to describe yield across diverse light regimes.

To address this, a three-level calibration strategy was adopted based on the seasonal s_d :

Level 1: Full light to $s_d \leq 0.12$ (threshold defined using a broken-line model)

Level 2: $0.12 < s_d \leq 0.29$ (moderate shading)

Level 3: $0.29 < s_d \leq 0.57$ (high shading)

For each level, parameters ε , F_m and *DSRate1* (development rate from emergence to tuber initiation) were optimized using Scilab's 'fminsearch' function, minimizing the sum of squared deviations between observed and simulated yield.

3. Results

Throughout the manuscript, experimental treatments are referred to using the acronyms defined in Table 3 (FL, ST1, ST2, ST1+AT), while shading intensity is described quantitatively using mean and local shade depth values.

3.1. Weather conditions

Weather conditions during the growing seasons provide essential context for interpreting morphological and yield responses. Significant differences in both air temperature and rainfall were observed across the four cropping years (Fig. 4). The average air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) for the years 2021 to 2024 was 17.3, 18.5, 17.9, and 18.0, respectively. The average number of daily hours with temperatures above 25°C was 4.3, 6.3, 4.0, and 4.4, respectively. Notably, the year 2022 (Fig. 4) was the driest and most stressful for the potato crop, with elevated temperatures persisting from May until harvest. Total rainfall during the crop cycle was 191, 154, 399, and 507 mm across the four years, respectively. In 2024, abundant rainfall made irrigation unnecessary.

3.2. Morphological response to shading

In both 2021 and 2022 growing seasons, different shading conditions influenced the vegetative growth of potato plants (Figs. 5 and 6). Regarding plant height, the highest values were observed at 99 Days After Planting (DAP) in 2021: 66.0 cm, 70.7 cm, and 84.9 cm for FL, ST1, and ST2, respectively. Similarly, in 2022, peak values were reached at 94 DAP: 61.3 cm (FL), 70.4 cm (ST1), and 78.8 cm (ST2).

In 2021, the highest LAI values were measured at 66 DAP, showing moderate differences among treatments but consistently higher values under heavier shading: 2.3 (FL), 2.2 (ST1), and 2.6 (ST2).

SLA trends were more variable. In 2021, SLA tended to decrease when LAI increased, while in 2022, both LAI and SLA followed similar trends. SLA consistently increased with increasing shading: average values for FL, ST1, and ST2 were 246.9, 280.0, and 328.7 $\text{cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ in 2021 and 313.2, 357.0, and 403.0 $\text{cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ in 2022.

3.3. Tuber yield

The trial was conducted under certified organic farming conditions. Across the four-year period, yield levels obtained under both full-light and agrivoltaic conditions were consistent with those reported for commercial organic potato production in Italy.

The four-year trial revealed a clear gradient in yield response to shading intensity, with moderate shading generally tolerated and heavy shading consistently detrimental (Fig. 7). In the first year (2021), marketable yields reached 51.5 t ha^{-1} under full light but declined to 38.9 t ha^{-1} in ST1 and 28.0 t ha^{-1} in ST2, corresponding to significant reductions in tuber number (60.3, 52.0, and 46.7 m^{-2} , respectively). Dry matter content (DMC) remained stable across treatments (0.22–0.20 g g^{-1} fresh weight), (Fig. 7). The second year (2022), characterized by drier and hotter conditions, confirmed this trend: yields dropped from 38.0 t ha^{-1} in FL to 29.9 and 24.6 t ha^{-1} in ST1 and ST2, respectively, while tuber numbers showed no significant differences. Interestingly, DMC was significantly affected, with values declining slightly from 0.20 in FL to 0.19 and 0.18 (g g^{-1} fresh weight) in the shaded treatments (Fig. 7). In 2023, when only FL and ST2 were tested, the shading penalty was most pronounced: yields fell from 27.4 to 16.1 t ha^{-1} , tuber number from 37.4 to 25.3 (tuber m^{-2}) and DMC from 0.19 to 0.18 (g g^{-1} fresh weight), with all differences significant. In contrast, the 2024 experiment, which introduced the anti-tracking (AT) strategy, produced a different outcome. While yields under FL and ST1 were statistically similar (30.3 and 29.9 t ha^{-1}), the AT treatment resulted in a statistically significant increase in productivity (32.7 t ha^{-1} ; Table 5), occasionally exceeding the full-light reference. Neither tuber number (48.9, 43.3, and 38.8 tuber m^{-2}) nor DMC (0.20, 0.19, and 0.18, g g^{-1} fresh weight) were significantly affected that year. Overall, these results demonstrate that potato crops can maintain yields under moderate shading but are highly penalized under heavier shade, while dynamic shading reduction during tuber initiation (AT) offers a promising management option to mitigate yield losses.

Fig. 4. Daily rainfall and air mean temperature (circles) in the four years recorded by the weather station installed nearby the AV installation. Colors of circles are associated with the number of daily hours with mean temperature > 26 °C. The grey band represents min and max temperature. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.).

3.4. Tuber size distribution and estimated Weibull parameters

Experimental conditions and cropping year had a variable effect on the proportion of unmarketable tubers, (TSD), and the parameters of the Weibull function (Fig. 8). The proportion of undersized tubers (< 25 mm) ranged from 1.8 % to 15.6 %, with the lowest values observed in 2021, the only year in which the Kuroda variety was used. In 2021 the estimated values of μ (distribution mean, formula 4) for FL, ST1 and ST2 were respectively 60.2 mm, 57.8 mm and 56.8 mm.

In 2022 and 2023, a slight increase in the proportion of undersized tubers was observed under increasing shading intensity, from FL to ST2.

Regarding the Weibull parameters, the highest scale factor (λ) was found in 2021 for FL ($\lambda = 65.1$), and the lowest in 2023 for ST2 ($\lambda = 50.2$). The shape factor (k) showed a similar trend: the highest value was recorded in 2021 for FL ($k = 5.6$), and the lowest in 2023 for ST2 ($k = 3.6$). Thus, in 2021 and 2022, both λ and k decreased with increasing shade, indicating a higher proportion of larger tubers under full light. In 2023, shading still reduced λ and k , but the differences were less pronounced: $\lambda = 52.0$ and $k = 3.8$ for FL, versus $\lambda = 50.2$ and $k = 3.6$ for ST2. In 2022 the estimated values of μ for FL, ST1 and ST2 were respectively 52.7 mm, 50.25 mm and 49.2 mm while in 2023 the estimated μ revealed minimal difference between FL and ST2: 46 mm and 45.3 mm respectively.

Fig. 5. Seasonal progression of potato morphological traits in 2021 under different experimental treatments: full-light control (FL), standard sun-tracking agrivoltaic configuration (ST1), and high-shade agrivoltaic configuration (ST2). Each panel shows the mean \pm standard deviation for plant height (top), LAI (middle), and SLA (bottom). Measurements represent the average of three plants per subplot across four subplots per treatment ($n = 12$).

In contrast, in 2024 both λ and k increased slightly under shaded conditions: λ values were 58.0 for FL, 59.7 for ST1, and 60.8 for ST1+AT; k values were 3.6, 3.9, and 3.8, respectively. As observed for λ and k under shade conditions μ increased. For FL, ST1 and ST1+AT values were respectively 52.2 mm, 54.0 mm and 55.0 mm.

3.5. Relationship between shade depth and tuber yield

Even after normalization the relationship between shade depth (s_d) and relative yield (yr) displayed substantial scatter, particularly for s_d values between 15 % and 25 % (Fig. 9). The variation in s_d within each scenario (based on mapped values) differed markedly: the narrowest range was observed in the ST1+AT scenario ($s_{dmin} = 10$ %, $s_{dmax} = 21$ %), while the widest was found in ST2 for the year 2022 ($s_{dmin} = 29$ %, $s_{dmax} = 57$ %).

The highest yr was obtained under ST1+AT, with values consistently above 1 across all s_d values. Conversely, the lowest relative yields were observed in the ST2 scenario during 2023, with values ranging from 0.55 to 0.77, corresponding to an average yield reduction of 35 %. The parameters for the fitted models (Eq. (4)) were as follows:

Single segment model: $b = 0.009$, $s_{dC} = 0$

Broken line model: $b = 0.011$, $s_{dC} = 12.1$

The broken line model provided a better fit (RMSE = 0.099, $R^2 = 0.735$) than the single segment model (RMSE = 0.115, $R^2 = 0.637$). In the scatter plot (Fig. 10), the greatest deviations from the 1:1 line (observed vs. simulated) occurred around a relative yield of 1, which impaired model performance indicators. Specifically:

Broken line model: $EF_1 = 0.604$, $C = 0.079$

Single segment model: $EF_1 = 0.519$, $C = 0.096$

Fig. 6. Seasonal progression of potato morphological traits in 2022 under different experimental treatments: full-light control (FL), standard sun-tracking agrivoltaic configuration (ST1), and high-shade agrivoltaic configuration (ST2). Each panel shows the mean \pm standard deviation for plant height (top), LAI (middle), and SLA (bottom). Measurements represent the average of three plants per subplot across four subplots per treatment ($n = 12$).

3.6. Daisy simulations

The initial fit between observed and simulated tuber yield values, using a single set of cultivar-specific parameters (default for *Solanum tuberosum* cv. Agria), was not satisfactory. Although calibration of selected parameters (Table 6) slightly improved the model performance, the overall fit remained inadequate to interpret the observed variability across different shading conditions (goodness-of-fit indices not shown). A marked improvement was achieved by adopting a “stratified parameterization”, where independent calibrations were performed for different levels of seasonal shade depth. The optimized values for the three shading strata are summarized in Table 6. Notably, the value of F_m (maximum gross assimilation rate) decreased with increasing shade intensity (Fig. 11, left), from 3.802 (low shade) to 3.22 (medium) and 2.257 (high shade). In contrast, the parameter ϵ (initial light use efficiency at low irradiance) increased progressively: 0.083, 0.089, and 0.1797.

Another stratified parameter, $DSRate1$ (development rate from emergence to tuberisation), showed a clear decreasing trend: 0.065, 0.0611, and 0.0525. This implies a physiological delay in tuber formation under increasing shade conditions. Simulated photosynthetic response curves for the three strata, using the Goudriaan and van Laar [30] photosynthesis sub-model implemented in Daisy, are shown in Fig. 11 (right). Especially under high shade, a rapid saturation of photosynthesis is evident at PAR levels slightly above 200 W m⁻², confirming a transition to light-limited assimilation. The overall model performance was evaluated by comparing observed and simulated tuber yield across the entire range of seasonal shade depth and test years (Fig. 12). The stratified model version (blue symbols, Fig. 12) yielded minimal deviations from observed values (Fig. 13). Fit indices were as follows: RMSE = 3.94 t ha⁻¹ EF1 (Modified Modelling Efficiency) = 0.559 Relative MAE (C) = 0.10 R² = 0.808. These results indicate that the stratified approach allowed the model to better capture crop responses to shade, especially in the higher shading environments where

Fig. 7. Box plot and results of the Tukey test after ANOVA for marketable tuber yield, (t ha⁻¹), tuber number (tuber m⁻²) and Dry Matter Content (g g⁻¹ fresh weight) obtained in the four years of the experiment. Boxes extend from Q1 to Q3 (interquartile range, IQR) and highlight the median. Whiskers extend to Q1/Q3 +/- 1.5*the IQR. Compact letters display statistically significant differences with $p < 0.05$.

Table 5
Anova results for marketable tuber yield, tuber number and DMC.

Year	Source	df	Tuber yield		Tuber number		DMC	
			F value	Pr(>F)	F value	Pr(>F)	F value	Pr(>F)
2021	Scenario	2	18.097	0.0426*	6.19316	0.0348 *	0.438522	0.6641 ns
	Harv. plots	6	5.58997	0.0187*	1.3665	0.4302 ns	8.704482	0.0518 ns
2022	Scenario	2	5.34516	0.0295 *	3.17609	0.0904 ns	12.67518	0.0024 **
	Harv. plots	9	4.0347	0.0007 ***	1.04081	0.4233 ns	0.889831	0.5415 ns
2023	Scenario	2	7.88155	0.0105 *	5.17942	0.0319 *	5.02791	0.0342 *
	Harv. plots	9	6,87,152	0.0062 **	4.32866	0.0256 *	1.052821	0.4765 ns
2024	Scenario	2	6.11516	0.0148 *	1.32663	0.3016 ns	1.3407253	0.2982 ns
	Harv. plots	12	0.509199	0.8921 ns	0.67447	0.7616 ns	0.9001123	0.5572 ns

Fig. 8. Tuber size distribution according to year (rows) and scenarios (columns). The histograms on the left side of each panel represent tubers belonging to non marketable size class (<25 mm). The solid lines represent the probability densities obtained by fitting the Weibull distribution. The dashed lines represent the densities obtained under full-light conditions (FL) in the year identified by the row. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 9. Relationship between relative yield and shade depth (%) from all shading areas in the different AV scenarios over four years of testing. Open symbols represent the average relative yields observed in the test areas at different shade depths for each experimental year: 2021 (○), 2022 (□), 2023 (△), and 2024 (◇). The 'broken line' and 'straight line' represent the selected models describing the relationship between shade depth and relative yield. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

standard parameter sets failed. These results highlight the relevance of accounting for physiological plasticity in crop models under heterogeneous light environments, particularly in APV systems where shade is both structural and dynamic.

4. Discussion

This study brings together the results of four consecutive years of potato cultivation under a commercial agrivoltaic system, providing one of the most comprehensive datasets currently available for a shade-sensitive crop. By integrating multiple shading configurations, including an anti-tracking (AT) strategy, we were able to evaluate both the penalties and the adaptive potential of potatoes grown under heterogeneous light environments. The use of a temporally targeted AT strategy aligns with recent advances in agrivoltaic system management, where dynamic tracking has been proposed as a means to optimize trade-offs between crop performance and energy production rather than as a season-long operating mode. In this respect, our results are consistent with the conceptual framework proposed by Grubbs et al. [33], who highlighted the potential of phase-specific tracking adjustments to mitigate yield penalties; however, direct quantitative comparisons are limited by differences in crop, system configuration, and

experimental objectives.

The multi-year perspective is particularly valuable, as it captures interannual variability in weather conditions, management, and cultivar performance, thereby offering a robust assessment of yield responses and tuber quality traits in real farming contexts.

Although not the primary focus of the study, the organic farming context represents an additional element of interest, as agrivoltaic field experiments conducted under certified organic management remain relatively scarce in the current literature [6]. The yield stability observed across contrasting light regimes suggests a notable degree of crop resilience under organic conditions and supports the agronomic feasibility of agrivoltaic systems in this production context.

Previous studies on potatoes under APV provide contrasting outcomes. Schulz et al. [5] and Campana et al. [7] consistently reported yield reductions under shade, while Weselek et al. [6] and Trommsdorff et al. [9] observed benefits in dry conditions, when APV mitigated heat and drought stresses.

During these experiments, irrigation ensured that water was not limiting, so such protective effects were less relevant. Under these well-watered conditions, the fact that marketable yields under the standard sun-tracking configuration (ST1), characterized by a low ground cover ratio (GCR ~ 0.135) and a low mean seasonal shade depth (21 %), were comparable to those under full light (FL) highlights the crop's tolerance to partial reductions in radiation rather than a response to stress mitigation.

The similarity in marketable tuber yields between the standard sun-tracking configuration (ST1) and full-light conditions (FL) observed in some seasons suggests that potato can tolerate a moderate reduction in incident radiation without yield penalties, remaining within its shade-tolerance range. This interpretation is consistent with previous findings reporting a relatively broad tolerance of potato to partial shading [5].

However, shade fraction alone does not fully capture the complexity of the microclimatic environment created under agrivoltaic systems. Elevated air temperatures typical of Mediterranean conditions may increase the metabolic costs associated with shade acclimation, thereby amplifying the physiological burden imposed by reduced radiation. Such interactions between temperature and light availability are well documented in plant ecophysiology [34,35] and may partly explain the variability of yield responses observed across seasons.

These physiological constraints are expected to be particularly relevant during the tuber initiation phase. While the roles of temperature and photoperiod in regulating tuber initiation are well established [36, 37], the influence of shading remains comparatively less explored. Early

Fig. 10. Scatter plot of observed relative yields (yr) and yields estimated for the two models. The dotted black line represents a perfect prediction.

Table 6

Different sets of Daisy crop parameters for the Alouette potato. They were derived from Agria sets Daisy library (<https://daisy.ku.dk/>) and modified with the calibration process.

Parameter symbol and unit	Description	Source	Shading environment (S_d ranges)		
			0 – 0.12	0.12 – 0.28	0.29 – 0.57
F_m (g CO ₂ (m ² h) ⁻¹)	Maximum gross assimilation rate.	Stratif. Calib.	3.802	3.22	2.257
ϵ (g/m ² /h) / (W/m ²)	Initial light use efficiency at low intensity	Stratif. Calib.	0.083	0.089	0.1797
SpLAI (m ² (g DM) ⁻¹)	Specific Leaf Area Index	Observed*	0.028	0.0319	0.0365
DSLAI05 (m ² m ²)	Parameter that forces LAI to be 0.5 at a certain development stage (DS)	General Calib.	0.3677	0.3677	0.3677
DSRate1 (DS D-1)	Rate of development from emergence to tuberisation.	Stratif. Calib.	0.065	0.0611	0.0525
DSRate2 (DS D-1)	Rate of development from tuberisation to harvest.	General Calib.	0.011	0.011	0.011

* Mean values of observed SLA data collected in years 2021 and 2022.

studies [38,39] provided foundational insights, and more recent work has shown that high shade levels can reduce tuber number, highlighting the sensitivity of this developmental phase to light availability [5].

Consistent with this interpretation, increased shading was generally associated with a reduction in tuber number and a shift in tuber size distribution toward smaller size classes. This shift toward smaller tubers was reflected by lower values of the Weibull mean diameter μ and scale λ parameters, indicating a redistribution toward smaller size classes. Similar patterns have been reported in aeroponic systems [40] and field studies [41], demonstrating that radiation availability during tuber initiation strongly influences tuber set and size distribution. Under conditions where radiation differences between treatments were limited, changes in tuber size appeared to reflect alterations in assimilate partitioning rather than enhanced tuber initiation, suggesting a strong sensitivity of tuber size distribution to sink–source balance under non-limiting conditions. This mechanism also explains the occasional

increase in the Weibull scale parameter (λ) observed under intermediate shading in climatically favourable conditions (e.g. ST1 in 2024), where a slightly reduced tuber number likely alleviated intra-plant competition for assimilates, resulting in larger average tuber size despite comparable radiation availability.

Dry matter content showed variable responses to shading across seasons, with no consistent deviation from full-light conditions. This variability indicates that shading effects on tuber composition are strongly modulated by environmental context and are likely secondary to broader source–sink dynamics and water availability, as previously reported [42,43].

The simulated results obtained with the Daisy model confirm that a stratified calibration approach substantially improves the reliability of Daisy simulations under APV conditions. The variation of key parameters - such as F_m , ϵ , and **DSRate1** - suggests distinct physiological adjustments in response to shade, consistent with known mechanisms of acclimation. Moreover, the model captured inter-annual yield variability across a wide range of shade depths, highlighting its potential for predictive applications. The following section provides a critical analysis of the results implications, the physiological plausibility of the stratified parameters, and the prospects for improving crop models to better represent shade responses in APV systems.

4.1. Physiological interpretation of the stratified parameters

The stratified responses observed in our trials - including yield reductions under heavy shading, SLA increases, and shifts in tuber size distribution - point to underlying acclimation processes that cannot be explained by shade level alone. These outcomes are consistent with physiological trade-offs well documented in plant ecophysiology, such as the reallocation of nitrogen within the canopy and the adjustment of photosynthetic capacity across leaf layers [44].

In this framework, our stratified parameterization is not merely a statistical adjustment but reflects the biological plausibility of acclimation mechanisms. By stratifying F_m and ϵ , the model reflects this adaptive shift without requiring full mechanistic complexity. These coordinated changes in F_m and ϵ reflect a typical shade-acclimation response, as illustrated in Fig. 14, where both biochemical and morphological adjustments contribute to maintaining canopy photosynthesis under reduced and variable light. Importantly, the stratified parameterization was not derived from purely statistical considerations, but was informed by well-established concepts in plant ecophysiology describing shade acclimation and source–sink adjustments under reduced and heterogeneous radiation [34].

Fig. 11. (Left panel) Values of parameters F_m (maximum gross assimilation rate, black line) and ϵ (initial slope of the light response curve, blue line) obtained for different shading levels using the stratified calibration approach. F_m shows a decreasing trend with increasing shade depth, while ϵ increases. (Right panel) Simulated canopy photosynthesis curves for the three shade levels using the Daisy crop model. The curve for the high-shade condition exhibits early saturation of photosynthesis at PAR values just above 200 W m⁻², indicating light limitation. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 12. Observed tuber yields (open markers \circ , \square , \triangle , \diamond) and stratified model predictions (filled markers \bullet , \blacksquare) plotted against seasonal shade depth for different experimental years. The stratified Daisy model shows good agreement across shading levels, capturing both the magnitude and interannual variability of yield reduction under agrivoltaic conditions. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

This approach therefore strengthens the interpretation of yield penalties as the cumulative result of altered nitrogen partitioning, canopy structure, and photosynthetic efficiency under APV. By linking experimental observations with a process-based framework, this analysis highlights that acclimation dynamics, though often overlooked in current crop models, are indispensable for understanding potato performance under variable shading. Taken together, this stratified interpretation not only explains the yield responses observed under APV but

also delineates a pathway for future work. By showing how physiological acclimation mechanisms can be integrated into crop modelling, our study highlights both the progress already achieved and the need to extend these approaches further. This naturally leads to a consideration of the current limitations of our work and the future implications for APV research.

Fig. 13. Scatter plots of observed and simulated tuber yields. The model was calibrated with the observed values obtained in years 2021–2023 (symbols ○, □, △), while the results of year 2024 were used for validation purpose (symbols ◇). Each symbol represents the mean value of four replicates (plots). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

4.2. Morphological acclimation under shading

The results show that potato plants exhibited clear morphological acclimation to shading, with increased height, altered LAI, and consistently higher SLA under heavier shade (Figs. 5 and 6). These responses align with modern syntheses on shade acclimation and avoidance [45–47] and are consistent with APV field evidence on potatoes and mixed rotations [5,6]. Under APV, dynamic structural shade and sun–shade transitions likely intensify these adjustments. The increase in SLA followed the shading gradient, modest in ST1 and more pronounced in ST2, confirming a progressive morphological acclimation. These adjustments illustrate the interplay between shade avoidance and shade acclimation mechanisms operating under APV conditions. The elongation of stems and petioles, together with the increased leaf angle, are typical avoidance responses that enhance light interception during transient sunflecks. Conversely, the observed increase in SLA and the maintenance of LAI under shading reflect true acclimation processes, allowing the canopy to optimize light capture and carbon gain under reduced irradiance. This coexistence of avoidance and acclimation traits likely represents a flexible strategy enabling potatoes to maintain productivity under the dynamic shading patterns characteristic of agrivoltaic systems.

At the same time, taller canopies suggest enhanced apical dominance. This elongation response is classically associated with shade-avoidance syndromes, triggered by a reduction in the Red:FarRed (R:FR) light ratio under canopy or structural shade. Such shifts in light quality activate phytochrome signalling, promoting stem elongation to outgrow neighbouring structures [45]. This dual response – biochemical (reflected in F_m , ϵ) and morphological (SLA, height) – constitutes the essence of light acclimation and must be integrated in crop models designed for APV systems [48]. Taken together, these acclimation responses highlight both the potential and the complexity of potato performance under APV. At the same time, they also underscore the need to acknowledge some limitations of our study and outline directions for future research.

In agrivoltaic systems characterized by strong spatial and temporal heterogeneity of light, changes in both light quantity and quality occur simultaneously [49], as a direct consequence of panel geometry, tracking strategy, and sun–canopy interactions [2]. In particular,

Plant acclimation to shade

Fig. 14. Conceptual diagram illustrating plant acclimation to shading in agrivoltaic (APV) systems. Shading simultaneously reduces photosynthetically active radiation (\downarrow PAR) and the red to far-red light ratio (\downarrow R:FR), triggering two complementary acclimation pathways. On the biochemical side (left), reduced PAR affects the redox state of Photosystem II (PSII), leading to regulatory adjustments in nitrogen allocation within the canopy. These adjustments are represented by a reduced Rubisco investment ($\downarrow F_m$) and an increased light-use efficiency ($\uparrow \epsilon$), supporting photosynthetic performance under low and fluctuating irradiance. On the morphological side (right), changes in R:FR are perceived by phytochrome photoreceptors and induce classical shade-avoidance responses, including stem elongation and the formation of thinner leaves, resulting in increased plant height and higher (SLA). Together, these coordinated biochemical and morphological responses illustrate the physiological basis of canopy acclimation to heterogeneous light environments under APV systems and provide a conceptual framework supporting the stratified modelling approach adopted in this study.

modifications in the red to far-red ratio act as a key regulatory signal driving both morphological and physiological acclimation responses. Recent modelling studies have highlighted that this intrinsic heterogeneity poses substantial challenges for crop simulation under APV conditions [18,50]. In the absence of an explicit representation of acclimation processes, model calibration inevitably relies on empirical, site- or sector-specific parameterizations, as adopted in the present study, which can improve local model performance but may limit physiological interpretability and transferability across systems. From this perspective, incorporating light acclimation mechanisms represents a necessary step toward more realistic and generalizable crop modelling in agrivoltaic systems.

4.3. Limits and future implications

A first limitation of this study lies in the specificity of the experimental setting. Potatoes were grown under controlled irrigation, which may have masked potential protective effects of agrivoltaic systems against drought and heat stress. Future trials under rainfed conditions, or under imposed water limitations, will be required to better quantify the extent to which APV can mitigate combined thermal and water stresses.

Second, while this analysis addressed shade fraction as the main explanatory variable, this metric does not fully capture the spatio-

temporal dynamics of light quality and canopy microclimate. Extending field measurements to include spectral composition, canopy temperature, and soil water balance would provide a more comprehensive representation of plant–environment interactions under APV conditions.

Third, this study did not explicitly quantify energy yield or the trade-off between electricity production and crop performance. Although system-level indicators such as the Land Equivalent Ratio are increasingly used to compare agrivoltaic configurations, their meaningful application requires concurrent and internally consistent measurements of both crop and energy performance, which were beyond the scope of the present study. Integrating agronomic trials with energy simulations, particularly in dual-axis tracking systems, will be essential to assess the real co-benefits and operational limits of dynamic shading strategies.

The yield response observed in 2024 under the ST1+AT treatment, which was not fully explained by differences in shade fraction alone, highlights the need for deeper physiological investigation. Linking morphological acclimation with photosynthetic plasticity, nitrogen allocation, and responses to fluctuating light may pave the way toward a more mechanistic understanding of crop resilience under APV conditions.

Finally, the stratified calibration adopted in this study should not be interpreted as a fully predictive modelling exercise. Rather, it represents a descriptive and exploratory approach aimed at translating well-established plant physiological responses to shading into a process-based modelling framework. While additional datasets across sites, cultivars, and seasons are required for robust validation, the present four-year experiment provides a valuable empirical basis for identifying key parameters, guiding model development, and defining priorities for future data collection in agrivoltaic systems.

5. Conclusions

This four-year field study demonstrates that potato crops exhibit a moderate but consistent tolerance to shading under agrivoltaic conditions. Marketable yields were maintained under moderate shade levels (approximately 15–20 %), while progressively declining under heavier shading, largely in proportion to reductions in incident radiation. Yield losses at higher shade fractions were primarily associated with reduced tuber number and an increased proportion of undersized tubers, rather than with changes in tuber dry matter content.

Morphological acclimation responses, including increased plant height, altered canopy structure, and higher SLA, indicate a clear capacity of potato to adjust to reduced and heterogeneous light environments. However, these adjustments appear to entail physiological costs, particularly under Mediterranean conditions where elevated temperatures may interact with light limitation to constrain productivity. The application of a temporally targeted anti-tracking strategy resulted in partial yield recovery in one season, suggesting that dynamic light management during sensitive phenological phases may offer opportunities to mitigate shading effects, although its effectiveness remains context-dependent.

Beyond agronomic outcomes, this study highlights the need for crop models used in agrivoltaic research to better represent light acclimation processes. The results support the refinement of process-based models to account for spatially and temporally heterogeneous radiation, canopy acclimation, and tuber size distribution dynamics. Future research should extend these findings across different cultivars, environments, and agrivoltaic configurations, and integrate agronomic and energy perspectives to support the sustainable design and management of agrivoltaic systems.

Ethical statement

This study did not involve human participants or animals.

All experimental activities were conducted in accordance with standard agronomic practices and applicable institutional and national

guidelines.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Michele Colauzzi: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Gabriele Sortino:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Eleonora Potenza:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology. **Yuri Bellone:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Giorgio Impollonia:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Data curation. **Amirhossein Nik Zad:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology. **Michele Croci:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Giancarlo Ghidese:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Iliana Le Bossene:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Stefano Amaducci:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] G.A. Barron-Gafford, M.A. Pavao-Zuckerman, R.L. Minor, L.F. Sutter, I. Barnett-Moreno, D.T. Blackett, M. Thompson, K. Dimond, A.K. Gerlak, G.P. Nabhan, J. E. Macknick, Agrivoltaics provide mutual benefits across the food–energy–water nexus in drylands, *Nat. Sustain.* 2 (9) (2019) 848–855, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0364-5>.
- [2] C. Dupraz, H. Marrou, G. Talbot, L. Dufour, A. Nogier, Y. Ferard, Combining solar photovoltaic panels and food crops for optimising land use: towards new agrivoltaic schemes, *Renew. Energy* 36 (10) (2011) 2725–2732, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2011.03.005>.
- [3] H. Marrou, L. Guillioni, L. Dufour, C. Dupraz, J. Wery, Microclimate under agrivoltaic systems: is crop growth rate affected in the partial shade of solar panels? *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 177 (2013) 117–132, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2013.04.012>.
- [4] S. Amaducci, X. Yin, M. Colauzzi, Agrivoltaic systems to optimise land use for electric energy production, *Appl. Energy* 220 (2018) 545–561, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.03.081>.
- [5] V.S. Schulz, S. Munz, K. Stolzenburg, J. Hartung, S. Weisenburger, S. Graeff-Hönninger, Impact of different shading levels on growth, yield and quality of potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.), *Agronomy* 9 (6) (2019), <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy9060330>.
- [6] A. Weselek, A. Bauerle, J. Hartung, Agrivoltaic system impacts on microclimate and yield of different crops within an organic crop rotation in a temperate climate, *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 41 (2001) 59, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-021-00714-y>.
- [7] P.E. Campana, B. Stridh, S. Amaducci, M. Colauzzi, Optimisation of vertically mounted agrivoltaic systems, *J. Clean. Prod.* (2021) 325, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.129091>.
- [8] H.J. Lee, H.H. Park, Y.O. Kim, Y.I. Kuk, Crop cultivation underneath Agro-Photovoltaic Systems and its effects on Crop growth, yield, and photosynthetic efficiency, *Agronomy* 12 (8) (2022), <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy12081842>.

- [9] M. Trommsdorff, J. Kang, C. Reise, S. Schindele, G. Bopp, A. Ehmann, A. Weselek, P. Högy, T. Oberfell, Combining food and energy production: design of an agrivoltaic system applied in arable and vegetable farming in Germany, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* (2021) 140, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.110694>.
- [10] M. Trommsdorff, I.S. Dhal, Ö.E. Özdemir, D. Ketzler, N. Weinberger, C. Rösch, Chapter 5 - Agrivoltaics: solar power generation and food production, in: S. Gorjian, P.E. Campana (Eds.), *Solar Energy Advancements in Agriculture and Food Production Systems*, Academic Press, 2022, pp. 159–210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-89866-9.00012-2>.
- [11] C.H. Thum, K. Okada, Y. Yamasaki, Y. Kato, Impacts of agrivoltaic systems on microclimate, grain yield, and quality of lowland rice under a temperate climate, *Field Crop. Res.* 326 (2025) 109877, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2025.109877>.
- [12] C. Dupraz, Assessment of the ground coverage ratio of agrivoltaic systems as a proxy for potential crop productivity, *Agroforestry Systems, Springer Science and Business Media B.V.*, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-023-00906-3>.
- [13] A. Chatzipanagi, N. Taylor, C. Thirl, A. Jaeger-Waldau, E. Dunlop, R. Kenny, Agri-photovoltaics (Agri-PV): How Multi-Land Use Can Help Deliver Sustainable Energy and Food, European Commission, 2022. JRC Report JRC129225 Available at: <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC129225>.
- [14] G. Vico, S. Manzoni, S. Palmroth, G. Katul, Effects of stomatal delays on the economics of leaf gas exchange under intermittent light regimes, *New Phytol.* 192 (3) (2011) 640–652, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-8137.2011.03847.x>.
- [15] H. Marrou, L. Dufour, J. Wery, How does a shelter of solar panels influence water flows in a soil-crop system? *Eur. J. Agron.* 50 (2013) 38–51, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2013.05.004>.
- [16] V. Gupta, S.M. Gruss, D. Cammarano, S.M. Brouder, P.A. Bermel, M.R. Tuinstra, M. W. Gitau, R. Agrawal, Optimizing corn agrivoltaic farming through farm-scale experimentation and modeling, *Cell Rep. Sustain.* 1 (7) (2024) 100148, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crsus.2024.100148>.
- [17] Y. Bellone, M. Croci, G. Impollonia, A. Nik Zad, M. Colauzzi, P.E. Campana, S. Amaducci, Simulation-based decision support for Agrivoltaic systems, *Appl. Energy* (2024) 369, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2024.123490>.
- [18] S. Zainali, S.M. Lu, Á. Fernández-Solas, A. Cruz-Escabias, E.F. Fernández, T.E. K. Zidane, E.H. Honningdalsnes, M.M. Nygård, J. Leloux, M. Berwind, M. Trommsdorff, S. Amaducci, S. Gorjian, P.E. Campana, Modelling, simulation, and optimisation of agrivoltaic systems: a comprehensive review, *Appl. Energy* (2025) 386, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2025.125558>.
- [19] X. Yin, A.H.C.M. Schapendonk, P.C. Struik, Exploring the optimum nitrogen partitioning to predict the acclimation of C3 leaf photosynthesis to varying growth conditions, *J. Exp. Bot.* 70 (9) (2019) 2435–2447, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jxb/ery277>.
- [20] J. Graefe, W. Yu, O. Körner, A photosynthetic light acclimation model accounting for the effects of leaf age, chlorophyll content, and intra-leaf radiation transfer, *Front. Plant Sci.* 13 (2022) 889709, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2022.889709>.
- [21] A. Agostini, M. Colauzzi, S. Amaducci, Innovative Agrivoltaic systems to produce sustainable energy: an economic and environmental assessment, *Appl. Energy* 281 (2021) 116102, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.116102>.
- [22] E. Potenza, M. Croci, M. Colauzzi, S. Amaducci, Agrivoltaic system and modelling simulation: a case study of soybean (Glycine max L.) in Italy, *Horticulturae* 8 (12) (2022), <https://doi.org/10.3390/horticulturae8121160>.
- [23] A.J. Bussan, P.D. Mitchell, Copas ME, M.J. Drilias, Evaluation of the effect of density on potato yield and tuber size distribution, *Crop. Sci.* 47 (2007) 2462–2472, <https://doi.org/10.2135/cropsci2007.01.0026>.
- [24] T. Nemecek, J.O. Derron, O. Roth, A. Fischli, Adaptation of a crop-growth model and its extension by a tuber size function for use in a seed potato forecasting system, *Agric. Syst.* 52 (1996), [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0308-521X\(96\)00034-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0308-521X(96)00034-0).
- [25] E.B. Aliche, M. Oortwijn, T.P.J.M. Theeuwens, C.W.B. Bachem, H.J. van Eck, R.G. F. Visser, C.G. van der Linden, Genetic mapping of tuber size distribution and marketable tuber yield under drought stress in potatoes, *Euphytica* 215 (2019) 1–19, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10681-019-2508-0>.
- [26] K.Z. Travis, Use of a simple model to study factors affecting the size distribution of tubers in potato crops, *J. Agric. Sci.* 109 (1987) 563–571, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021859600081788>.
- [27] J. Widmer, B. Christ, J. Grenz, L. Norgrove, Agrivoltaics, a promising new tool for electricity and food production: a systematic review, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 192 (2024) 114277, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.114277>.
- [28] Scilab Enterprises, Scilab: free and open source software for numerical computation. <https://www.scilab.org>.
- [29] J.M. Yang, J.Y. Yang, S. Liu, G. Hoogenboom, An evaluation of the statistical methods for testing the performance of crop models with observed data, *Agric. Syst.* ISSN 127 (2014) 81–89, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2014.01.008>.
- [30] J. Goudriaan, H.H. Van Laar, Calculation of daily totals of the gross CO₂-assimilation of leaf canopies, *Neth. J. Agric. Sci.* 26 (1978) 373–382, <https://doi.org/10.18174/njas.v26i4.17080>.
- [31] G. Gómez-Ocampo, J. Cascales, A.L. Medina-Fraga, E.L. Ploschuk, A.I. Mantese, C. D. Crocco, et al., Transcriptomic and physiological shade avoidance responses in potato (*Solanum tuberosum*) plants, *Physiol. Plant.* 175 (4) (2023) e13991, <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppl.13991>.
- [32] X.C. Piao, D. Chakrabarty, E.-J. Hahn and K.-Y. Paek. 2004. The growth and photosynthetic characteristics of potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) plantlets as affected by Hydroponic solution pH and EC, light, and CO₂ Xuan-Chun. *J. Amer. Soc. Hort. Sci.* 129(1):100–105.
- [33] E.K. Grubbs, S.M. Gruss, V.Z. Schull, et al., Optimized agrivoltaic tracking for nearly-full commodity crop and energy production, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 191 (2024) 114018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.114018>.
- [34] F. Valladares, Ü. Niinemets, Shade tolerance, a key plant trait of complex nature and consequences, *Annu Rev. Ecol. Evol. Syst.* 39 (2008) 237–257, <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ecolsys.39.110707.173506>.
- [35] R.G. Walters, Towards an understanding of photosynthetic acclimation, *Ann. Bot.* 96 (4) (2005) 703–709, <https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mci205>.
- [36] Y.U. Kim, B.S. Seo, D.H. Choi, H.Y. Ban, B.W. Lee, Impact of high temperatures on the marketable tuber yield and related traits of potato, *Eur. J. Agron.* 89 (2017) 46–52, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2017.06.005>.
- [37] J. van Dam, P.L. Kooman, P.C. Struiki, Effects of temperature and photoperiod on early growth and final number of tubers in potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.), *Potato Res.* 39 (1996) 51–62, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02358206>.
- [38] D. Gray, J.C. Holmes, The effect of short periods of shading at different stages of growth on the development of tuber number and yield, *Potato Res.* 13 (1970), <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02355977>.
- [39] P. Sale, Effect of shading at different times on the growth and yield of the potato, *Aust. J. Agric. Res.* 27 (4) (1976) 557–566, <https://doi.org/10.1071/AR9760>.
- [40] R. Naik, M. Raju, S. Tengli, N. Gowda, S. Kn, Effect of season, root zone cooling and shading on growth and seed-tuber yield of potato through aeroponic technique. *1520, Pharma Innov. J.* 11 (6) (2022) 1520–1524. www.thepharmajournal.com.
- [41] P.J. O'Brien, D.M. Firman, E.J. Allen, Effects of shading and seed tuber spacing on initiation and number of tubers in potato crops (*Solanum tuberosum*), *J. Agric. Syst.* 130 (4) (1998) 431–449, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021859698005541>.
- [42] R.P. Mauro, A. Ierna, Tuber growth and nutritional traits in deficit irrigated potatoes, *Agronomy* 15 (5) (2025), <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy1505101>.
- [43] S.C. Ghosh, K. Asanuma, A. Kusutani, M. Toyota, Effects of shading on dry matter production, yield and nitrate reductase activity of potato under two levels of spacing, *Control Biol.* 40 (3) (2002), <https://doi.org/10.2525/ecb1963.40.259>.
- [44] Ü. Niinemets, Photosynthesis and resource distribution through plant canopies, *Plant Cell Environ.* 30 (2007) 1052–1071, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3040.2007.01683.x>.
- [45] C.L. Ballaré, R. Pierik, The shade-avoidance syndrome: multiple signals and ecological consequences, *Plant Cell Environ.* 40 (2017) 2530–2543, <https://doi.org/10.1111/pce.12914>.
- [46] J.R. Evans, H. Poorter, Photosynthetic acclimation of plants to growth irradiance: the relative importance of specific leaf area and nitrogen partitioning in maximizing carbon gain, *Plant Cell Environ.* 24 (2001) 755–767, <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-3040.2001.00724.x>.
- [47] H. Poorter, Ü. Niinemets, L. Poorter, I.J. Wright, R. Villar, Causes and consequences of variation in leaf mass per area (LMA): a meta-analysis, *New Phytologist* 182 (2009) 565–588, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-8137.2009.02830.x>.
- [48] K.J. Dietz, Efficient high light acclimation involves rapid processes at multiple mechanistic levels, *J. Exp. Bot.* 66 (9) (2015) 2401–2414, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jxb/eru505>.
- [49] Z. Tahir, N.Z. Butt, Implications of spatial-temporal shading in agrivoltaics under fixed tilt & tracking bifacial photovoltaic panels, *Renew. Energy* 190 (2022) 167–176, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2022.03.078>.
- [50] S. Ma Lu, M. Camporese, T. Ma, M. Haworth, P.E. Campana, Selective light transmission in agrivoltaics: modeling light spectra and photosynthetic rate, *Nexus* 2 (2025) 100074, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nexus.2025.100074>.

Further reading

- [51] J. Vos, P.E.L. van der Putten, Effects of partial shading of the potato plant on photosynthesis of treated leaves, leaf area expansion and allocation of nitrogen and dry matter in component plant parts, *Eur. J. Agron.* 14 (3) (2001) 209–220, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1161-0301\(00\)00090-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1161-0301(00)00090-3).
- [52] D. Vreugdenhil, L.I. Sergeeva, Gibberellins and tuberization in potato, *Potato Res.* 42 (1999) 471–481, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02358163>.
- [53] C. Yang, L. Li, Hormonal regulation in shade avoidance, *Front. Plant Sci.* 8 (2017), <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2017.01527>.
- [54] X. Yin, P.C. Struik, Modelling the crop: from system dynamics to systems biology, *J. Exp. Bot.* 61 (8) (2010) 2171–2183, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jxb/erp375>.